

ULTRASOUND DIAGNOSTICS IN SPLENOMEGALY

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Relevance. And one of the most dangerous complications is splenic rupture. When the spleen enlarges, the wall of its capsule becomes thinner and even a slight blow to its area can lead to rupture. This is a very dangerous condition, since bleeding from the spleen is quite difficult to stop. The spleen, being a lymphoid organ, in a number of diseases increases its activity, which is macroscopically manifested by an increase in its size - splenomegaly. At certain stages of disease development, splenomegaly may be the only symptom. There are different ways to detect splenomegaly using physical diagnostic methods and instrumental studies, however, the results of using different methods for assessing splenomegaly may contradict each other. The purpose of the work is a critical analysis of the facts about methods for examining the spleen and calculating the presence of splenomegaly. Splenomegaly is a rather dangerous condition. Since, due to an increase in the size of the organ, it causes anatomical defects and physiological disruptions in the functioning of the spleen.

Purpose of the study. Studying morphological changes in the spleen with splenomegaly using ultrasound.

Materials and methods of research. Materials collected from the medical history of patients of the Republican Research Center for Emergency Medicine of filially Bukhara.

Research results. Ultrasound elastography is a new developing technique that can be used in combination with other diagnostic methods in various fields of medicine. Splenomegaly is a rather dangerous condition. Since, due to an increase in the size of the organ, it causes anatomical defects and physiological disruptions in the functioning of the spleen. And one of the most dangerous complications is splenic rupture. When the spleen enlarges, the wall of its capsule becomes thinner and even a slight blow to its area can lead to rupture. This is a very dangerous condition, since bleeding from the spleen is quite difficult to stop. The spleen is usually clearly visible on ultrasound. Its echogenicity is approximately equal to that of the liver. Enlarged spleen or splenomegaly. The exact cause of an enlarged spleen is difficult to determine. Ultrasound of the spleen in most cases is performed as part of a comprehensive ultrasound of the abdominal cavity. It is not entirely rational to study the condition of only the spleen on ultrasound in isolation for many diseases.

Conclusions. Early ultrasound signs of established liver cirrhosis include splenomegaly, dilatation of the splenic vein and the formation of a collateral bed, which are the initial manifestations of portal hypertension syndrome. With subcompensated cirrhosis, a structural restructuring of the liver parenchyma occurs, characterized by a heterogeneous structure, an uneven and tuberosus contour, as well as deformation of the intrahepatic vessels. Late ultrasound signs of decompensated liver cirrhosis and severe portal hypertension include dilatation of the portal vein, a decrease in the velocity of blood flow in the portal system, the presence of ascites, a significant diameter of the paraumbilical vein and reverse blood flow in the branches of the portal vein.

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